

IODINATION. PART I. STUDIES ON THE EQUILIBRIUM IN SYSTEMS OF IODINE AND VARIOUS UNSATURATED ORGANIC COMPOUNDS IN THE DARK IN DIFFERENT NON-POLAR SOLVENTS.

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Investigations have been carried out on the thermal iodination of β -amylene and *hexo*-pinene in non-polar solvents like benzene, carbon tetrachloride and carbon disulphide. The reactions have been found to be reversible and the equilibrium constants have been determined under different experimental conditions.

The addition reactions of chlorine and bromine to unsaturated organic compounds have been studied in considerable details both in light as well as in the dark. But in comparison not much work has been done on addition reactions involving iodine in various polar and non-polar solvents. Such investigations, whether in the dark or in light, are troublesome, being for the most part very slow and disturbed by the incidence of a reverse reaction. Herz and Mylius (*Ber.*, 1907, 40, 2898) found that in the reaction between allyl alcohol and iodine in the dark in solutions of carbon tetrachloride, chloroform and carbon disulphide, bimolecular constants were obtained in the individual experiments, but they varied considerably with the concentration. The same reaction was also studied by Caughley and Robertson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 1323) both in the dark as well as in light in solutions of benzene, carbon tetrachloride and chloroform. But none of the above authors carried out the iodination of allyl alcohol in a systematic way—the last two authors carried out only one experiment in each solvent and concluded that the reaction was a simple bimolecular one. It is doubtful whether they would get bimolecular constants had they carried out the investigation in different concentrations of iodine. Another instance of iodination is the reversible formation and decomposition of ethylene iodide in the dark in solution of carbon tetrachloride studied by Polissar (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 52, 956). Schumacher (*ibid.*, 1930, 52, 3132) concluded that the reaction between iodine and ethylene in solution of carbon tetrachloride was homogeneous, proceeding by a chain reaction. Another example of iodination in the dark is the iodination of β -phenylpropionic acid in aqueous solution studied by Moelwyn-Hughes and Legard (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1933, 424). But this reaction is complicated due to the presence of tri-iodide (I_3^-) ion formed by potassium iodide and iodine. Muller (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1912, iv, 11, 1006) studied the iodination of oleic acid in

carbon tetrachloride and ethyl acetate solutions at different dilutions and found bimolecular reaction in each case.

Bythell and Robertson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 173) have studied the iodination of allyl alcohol, its acetate, benzoate and bromide and undecenoic acid, in different non-polar solvents, like carbon tetrachloride, hexane and chlorobenzene which form violet solutions and in polar solvents, like acetic acid and nitrobenzene, which form brown solutions. They observed that the reactions in polar solvents are homogeneous and termolecular and those in non-polar solvents are heterogeneous. The conclusion that the iodination in non polar solvents is heterogeneous is reached by these authors as a result of the following observations :—

(i) When the reaction vessel is packed with glass beads, the reaction proceeds more rapidly and this increase may be very considerable—the rate may be increased 15-fold.

(ii) On reducing the concentration of the reactants, a region is reached where there is a rapid diminution in velocity.

(iii) There is a limiting temperature above which the adsorbed film becomes unstable with a rapid diminution in reaction rate.

Recently Ogg and Priest (*J. Chem. Phys.*, 1939, 7, 736) have shown that thermal as well as photochemical reactions between iodine and cyclopropane in the gas phase are homogeneous and proceed by a chain reaction started by iodine atoms.

The most important investigations in this field were made by Gróh and Szelestey (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1927, 162, 333) who studied the iodination of erucic acid $[\text{CH}_3(\text{CH}_2)_7\text{CH}=\text{CH}(\text{CH}_2)_{11}\text{COOH}]$ in the dark in solutions of carbon tetrachloride and carbon disulphide at 35°, 15° and 13.8°. They found that the reaction velocity is proportional to the concentration of acid and to the cube of the iodine concentration, i.e. that the active molecule is I_3 . The reaction is expressed as $\text{I}_3 + \text{E} \rightleftharpoons \text{EI}_3 + 2\text{I}_2$. In neither solvent is the reaction complete, the equilibrium constant for carbon disulphide being 7.76 and for the carbon tetrachloride solution 19.8 at temperature 25°. The reaction velocity diminishes with rise in temperature. Gróh and Takacs (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1930, 149, 195) have studied the decomposition of erucic acid di-iodide and found that it is catalysed by iodine according to the equation,

The above authors gave convincing proof of their mechanism of the above reaction by showing that the velocity constant of decomposition found

experimentally according to the above reaction scheme was almost equal to that calculated from known equilibrium constant and the velocity constant of the formation of the di-iodide.

Thus we see that addition reactions involving iodine to unsaturated organic compounds in non-polar and polar solvents are complicated and full of controversy.

In this part and in subsequent parts* (II and III), we shall describe the results of investigations made on the thermal iodination of β -amylene, *d*-pinene and phenylacetylene in non-polar solvents, like benzene, carbon tetrachloride and carbon disulphide and in polar solvents, like acetic acid and ethyl alcohol. The reactions are reversible and do not proceed to completion. The reactions can be represented according to the equations :—

Iodine reacts with β -amylene both in the dark as well as in light. When the concentration of iodine is less $\{[\text{I}_2] \leq 0.02M\}$, the thermal reaction is immeasurably small but the reaction proceeds fast in light; but when $[\text{I}_2] > 0.02M$, there is an appreciable thermal reaction. The reaction between iodine and phenylacetylene in the dark in non-polar solvents is extremely small even with high initial concentrations of iodine, whereas it proceeds very fast in light.

In alcoholic solution there is an appreciable dark reaction with higher concentrations of iodine which becomes *nil*, when the concentration of iodine is low $\leq 0.025M$.

In this part results of investigations on the equilibrium in systems I_2 - β -amylene and I_2 -pinene in the dark have been described.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Reagents.—Merck's extra pure carbon tetrachloride, benzene and carbon disulphide, which were used in these investigations were further purified by allowing them to stand over fused CaCl_2 for three days and by subsequent distillation. Merck's resublimed iodine was used after

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further sublimation. B.D.H. purest β -amylene and Kahlbaum's *dextro*-pinene, further purified by distillation, were used in these investigations. β -Amylene forms peroxides in contact with air; so fresh solutions were prepared with freshly distilled acceptor after every two days so that no appreciable amount of peroxide was formed to vitiate our results.

Thermal Equilibrium.—The equilibria were studied at two different temperatures. For this purpose two series of reaction mixtures were kept in sealed glass tubes in each solvent. One series was kept in a bath at room temperature and the other series in a frigidaire. The initial concentration of iodine in each was determined and after two months, when equilibrium was attained, the concentration of iodine at equilibrium was determined in each case. The equilibrium constant K_E was calculated according to the relation,

$$K_E = \frac{[AI_2]_E}{[A]_E [I_2]_E}$$

where $[A]_E$, $[I_2]_E$ and $[AI_2]_E$ are the concentrations of the acceptor, iodine and the di-iodide at equilibrium.

The experimental data are recorded in Tables I-III, in which a and b denote initial concentrations of iodine and the acceptor respectively in g. mols./litre; a_E (0°), a_E (30°), a_E (27°) denote concentrations of iodine at equilibrium at 0° , 30° and 27° respectively and K_E , the equilibrium constant.

TABLE I

Acceptor— β -amylene.

Solvent.	b (mol.)	a (mol.)	a_E (0°). (mol.)	a_E (30°). (mol.)	K_E .	
					0° .	30° .
CCl ₄	0.1	0.0928	0.0516	0.065	13.58	5.92
	0.05	0.053	0.0372	0.0429	12.43	5.90
	0.025	0.0265	0.0213	0.0237	12.32	5.32
					Mean 12.78	5.71
C ₆ H ₆	0.198	0.110	0.0438	0.0630	11.48	4.94
	0.099	0.110	0.0625	0.0840	14.76	4.24
	0.148	0.055	0.0223	0.0363	12.72	3.98
					Mean 12.99	4.39
CS ₂	0.0444	0.0689	0.0567	0.0612	6.67	3.44
	0.178	0.103	0.0526	0.0703	7.51	3.30
					Mean 7.09	3.32

TABLE II.

Acceptor—pinene.

Solvent.	b. (mol).	a. (mol).	a _K (0°). (mol).	a _K (27°) (mol).	K _E .	
					0°.	27°.
CCl ₄	0·0400	0·04	0·013	0·0179	159·76	69·06
	0·0385	0·027	0·00655	0·0106	173·0	70·00
	Mean					166·38
C ₆ H ₆	0·021	0·0217	0·0123	0·0142	65·88	39·13
	0·042	0·0434	0·0188	0·230	75·19	41·06
	Mean					70·54
CS ₂	0·02	0·0211	0·0106	0·0132	104·2	49·45
	0·04	0·0423	0·0170	0·0230	101·3	40·54
	Mean					102·75

Heat of Reaction from Equilibrium Data.

The heat of reaction Q_v can be calculated from Vant Hoff's Isochore,

$$\frac{d \log K_E}{dT} = \frac{Q_v}{RT^2}$$

which on integration gives the expression,

$$\log K_E (T_1) - \log K_E (T_2) = \frac{Q_v}{R} \left[\frac{T_1 - T_2}{T_1 T_2} \right]$$

where $K_E (T_1)$ and $K_E (T_2)$ are the equilibrium constants at temperatures T_1° and T_2° absolute ($T_1 > T_2$); Q_v is the heat of reaction and R , the gas constant.

In the following table the heats of reaction between iodine and β -amylene and between iodine and d -pinene in different solvents are given.

TABLE III.

Solvent.	K_E $\theta = 0^\circ$	K_E $\theta = 30^\circ$	Q_v (calories)	K_E $\theta = 0^\circ$	K_E $\theta = 27^\circ$	Q_v (calories).
	β -Amylene.			d -Pinene.		
CCl ₄	12·78	5·71	-4443·0	166·38	69·53	-5291·0
C ₆ H ₆	12·90	4·39	-5984·0	70·54	40·09	-3427·0
CS ₂	7·09	3·32	-4185·0	102·75	44·99	-5012·0

DISCUSSION.

The reactions have the following characteristics:—

The equilibrium constant is independent of the initial concentrations of iodine and the acceptor but depends on temperature. With rise in temperature the constant diminishes rapidly which means that the reactions are exothermic. The heat of reaction is of the order -4000 to -6000 calories in the reaction between iodine and β -amylene and of the order -3000 to -5000 calories in the case of pinene.

In Part II of the series, it will be shown that the velocity of the addition of iodine to β -amylene and pinene in the dark is proportional to the concentration of the acceptor and to the cube of the iodine concentration. *i.e.*, the active molecule is I_3 , so that the reaction may be represented according to the equation,

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dx}{dt} &= k''[I_3][A] - k'[AI_3][I_2]^2 \\ &= k[I_2]^3[A] - k'[AI_3][I_2]^2. \end{aligned}$$

At equilibrium,
so that,

$$k[I_2]_e^3[A]_e = k'[AI_3]_e[I_2]_e^2$$

$$K_x = \frac{k}{k'} = \frac{[AI_3]_e [I_2]_e^2}{[I_2]_e^3 [A]_e} = \frac{[AI_3]_e}{[I_2]_e [A]_e}$$

where K_x is the equilibrium constant.

This relation has been found to hold good.

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